

SECURITY MEASURES TO ANTI-CRIMINALITY AND VICTIMOLOGY AS RESPONSE ACTIVITY IN THE UNIVERSITY FOR GLOBAL AWARENESS ON EXTENSION SERVICE TO HUMANITY

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ABSTRACT

The Criminal Justice Education of Capiz State University Dayao Satellite College Criminology Department has an extension and community involvement called as SARGE that play an important role in dealing with establishment and maintaining close partnership with stakeholders and other agencies in developing standardized response to all hazard response plans and trainings in cooperation with the local emergency responders and in Local Government Unit (LGU) and to provide relevant trainings and seminars regarding safety and security awareness for the community. It is becoming clear that SARGE Extension approach is needed to address multi-faceted community issues effectively. Such as in term of evaluation as to the disaster preparedness seminar conducted of Capiz State University, Dayao Satellite College Extension Services could be considered a successful event as seen on the evaluation result from the participants on its general satisfaction (*gilayon nga pag aksyon sang ginahinyo nga paghanas*) which have garnered an overall mean of 4.689823 which has a verbal description of “best” (*pinakamaayo*) the evaluation on basic martial arts training as to the general with 80% as to the whole that the training has satisfactorily met the expectation, 73.3 % as a whole the basic martial arts is the best training attended and 73.3% that the training surely change the outlook and practices as a whole with verbal description were best. The result on the evaluation of seminar-workshop on violence against women children as evaluated by the twenty-eight (28) participants. Data showed that the seminar-workshop on violence against women and children conducted by the Capiz State University, Dayao Satellite College, Criminology Department Extension Services was considered “best” (*pinakamaayo*) with the overall mean of 4.658335 by the participants. This implies that the program implemented by the extension services of Criminology Department in the field of violence against women and children seminar-workshop has a great impact

towards the participants. The “best” (*pinakamaayo*) result taken from the evaluation form of the participants implies that the program implemented by the extension services of Criminology Department in the field of Violence Against Women and their Children is helpful especially to the vulnerable mother and children of the participating community. While the Overall, training program based on the result of the evaluation in Basic Martial Arts, Violence against Women and Children and Disaster Preparedness was considered “best” (*pinakamaayo*) as the participants considered the training program to have satisfactorily met their expectations. The program monitoring of Seminar-workshop on Basic Martial Arts was Highly Observed with a mean of 4.6429 as evaluated as a whole of Barangay Ajogo, Barangay Barra, Barangay Dayao, and Barangay Dinginan. This implies that the seminar conducted by the Capiz State University Dayao Satellite College, Criminology Department Extension Office was properly practiced by the proponent. Furthermore, as to percentage result revealed that 71% were responded “Moderately Observed”, 21.4% were responded “Observed” and 7.4% were “Highly Observed”.

Keywords: *Sarge, Security and Safety, Extension Services, Basic Martial Arts, Violence Against Women and Children, Disaster Preparedness*

INTRODUCTION

The SARGE program, the community extension initiative of the Criminal Justice Education Department, plays a vital role in crime prevention and safety enhancement. Anchored on the crime prevention theory adopted by the Philippine National Police (PNP), the program draws upon various crime prevention approaches such as negotiating community support, developing action plans, and implementing strategies to reduce crime and foster security. As Johnson, Tilley, and Bowers (2015) emphasize, situational crime prevention methods, such as those in the SARGE program, are crucial in reducing opportunities for crime by altering the environment and improving safety measures. SARGE stands for S-ecurity and safety measures to A-nti criminality and victimology as R-esponse activity in the university for G-lobal awareness as E-xtension services to humanity, emphasizing the importance of safety, security, and crime awareness for communities.

A key concept of the program is that a safe community fosters real communal engagement, where crime prevention and injury reduction lead to an enhanced sense of well-being. Weisburd and Majmundar (2018) argue that social cohesion and community involvement are essential factors in creating safe, supportive environments that deter criminal activities. By promoting safety measures, the program enables individuals to take proactive steps in safeguarding themselves and their community. This principle aligns with the idea that community members have a crucial role to play in ensuring their own safety and that of others. Security awareness and training are, therefore, indispensable in any organization or community setting.

The effectiveness of community-based safety promotion has been well-documented both nationally and internationally. According to Weisburd, Farrington, and Gill (2016), problem-oriented policing and collaborative community programs have proven effective in reducing the incidence of crime, injuries, and violence while simultaneously promoting public health and well-being. Programs that focus on fire prevention, disaster preparedness, road safety, and safer public spaces have shown measurable success in improving safety at multiple levels. The involvement of the community and the formation of partnerships among local agencies and organizations are critical factors for the sustainability and success of such initiatives.

At CapSU Dayao Satellite College, the College of Criminal Justice Education is committed to equipping communities with the knowledge and resources needed to recognize potential safety risks and respond appropriately to emergencies. The SARGE program offers training in various areas, such as Basic Martial Arts, First Aid, Firefighting, and Disaster Preparedness. Lum, Koper, and Telep (2011) highlight that community safety initiatives that build local skills and knowledge contribute to long-term crime prevention success. The program also conducts seminars on important topics such as the Juvenile Justice Welfare Act and Violence Against Women and Children. These programs are designed not only to enhance individual skills but to foster a collaborative approach to community safety and crime prevention.

The overarching goal of the SARGE program is to empower communities, promoting safe and orderly living environments while addressing both current and future security challenges. Braga, Weisburd, and Turchan (2018) argue that sustained engagement between police, educational institutions, and communities is crucial for addressing security challenges holistically. By encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration and leveraging the resources available within the community, the program works to address these issues comprehensively. The university's role as an extension of the government further strengthens its capacity to act as a change agent, particularly in less privileged areas.

To ensure the effectiveness of the SARGE program, careful benchmarking activities are conducted to assess the skills, abilities, and capabilities of community members before training sessions begin. This assessment helps ensure that the training provided meets the actual needs of the community and is aligned with the available resources. The ultimate aim is to create a sustainable, long-term program that not only trains participants but also enhances their skills and capabilities to the fullest, avoiding the pitfall of incomplete or ineffective training initiatives.

In this regard, the government's role is to provide the technical and financial backing required to ensure the success of these programs. A key consideration in the implementation of the SARGE program is sustainability. Rather than a one-time training event, the program is designed to be ongoing and adaptive, meeting the evolving needs of the community while ensuring participants gain the full benefit of the training provided.

By fostering a collaborative relationship between the university and local barangays, the SARGE program embodies the principle that communities are essential partners in the broader goal of crime prevention and security enhancement. This collaboration not only ensures the program's success but also reinforces the idea that communities can actively contribute to their own safety and well-being. Through this approach, the SARGE program serves as an essential model for sustainable crime prevention and community development, helping to create safer, more resilient communities.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and assess the training needs of the residents of Barangay Barra, Dayao, Dinginan, and Libas in Roxas City, specifically focusing on Basic Martial Arts, Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC), and disaster preparedness. Furthermore, the study seeks to monitor the effectiveness of these training programs.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in the following areas?
 - 1.1. Agojo, Panay, Capiz;
 - 1.2. Barra, Roxas City;
 - 1.3. Dinginan, Roxas City; and
 - 1.4. Dayao, Roxas City?
2. What is the evaluation of the SARGE program by the respondents in terms of the following trainings?
 - 2.1. Basic Martial Arts;
 - 2.2. Seminar on Violence Against Women and Children; and
 - 2.3. Disaster Preparedness?
3. What is the monitoring status of the respondents regarding the following trainings?
 - 3.1. Basic Martial Arts;
 - 3.2. Seminar on Violence Against Women and Children; and
 - 3.3. Disaster Preparedness?
4. What plan can be proposed for the SARGE program based on the evaluation and monitoring of the conducted extension services?

METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodology employed in the study, detailing the research design, the procedures followed, the data collection process, and the subsequent analysis. Additionally, ethical considerations were addressed during the data collection phase to ensure the integrity and ethical standards of the research.

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive research design, which aims to systematically describe a situation, phenomenon, or population without manipulating any variables. According to Burns (2000), descriptive research is effective for presenting an accurate portrayal of situations or phenomena as they occur in their natural settings. The objective of this study was to determine the evaluation and monitoring practices of selected barangays, focusing on how these communities perceive their training programs in Basic Martial Arts, Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC), and disaster preparedness. The data was collected through surveys conducted among local residents and officials in Brgy. Agojo, Panay Capiz, as well as Barra, Dayao, and Dinginan in Roxas City. The descriptive design was chosen as it allows for a clear and detailed presentation of the participants' evaluation of the SARGE program and their monitoring of its effectiveness.

Research Environment and Research Participants

The study was conducted in four barangays: Brgy. Agojo in Panay, Capiz, and Barangays Barra, Dayao, and Dinginan in Roxas City. These barangays were chosen due to their active involvement in community safety programs, particularly through the SARGE extension program. The research took place in October 2020, during which time the selected communities were actively participating in training programs related to security and disaster preparedness.

The research participants included various community members who were directly involved in the program. Specifically, respondents comprised of members of the Barangay Peace Action Team (BPAT), barangay firefighters, barangay officials, and local residents. These participants were selected as they represent key stakeholders in the community's safety and crime prevention initiatives. In total, 117 individuals participated in the study, providing insights into their experiences with the SARGE program and its impact on their community.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents from Four Adopted Barangays in Panay, Capiz and Roxas City

Respondent	Sample Size	Percentage (%)
Barangay Agujo	28	23.93%
Barangay Barra	34	29.06%
Barangay Dayao	40	34.19%
Barangay Dinginan	15	12.82%
Total	117	100%

Research Instrument

This study, which employed a descriptive research design, aimed to evaluate and monitor the training needs of the residents of Barangays Agujo, Barra, Dayao, and Dinginan in Roxas City. To gather the necessary data, two sets of questionnaires were

used as the primary data collection instruments. Creswell (2014) highlights the use of questionnaires as an effective means of collecting quantitative data in descriptive research, making them a suitable choice for this study.

The first set of the questionnaire focused on collecting the socio-demographic information of the respondents, including their gender, age, and employment status, in relation to the monitoring process. It also gathered details about the type of training they had undergone.

The second set of the questionnaire aimed to assess the respondents' evaluation of the training programs, and the level of monitoring implemented in the identified barangays. This part included questions designed to measure the effectiveness of the programs and gauge the participants' perspectives on the overall impact of the training they received.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher developed a questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. Before its administration, the questionnaire was submitted to the research committee and faculty members for face and content validation. Following their recommendations, the necessary revisions were made. With the approval of the Barangay Chairman, the researcher then distributed the survey to the respondents. To ensure honest and accurate responses, the researcher clearly explained the purpose and objectives of the study to the participants prior to the survey.

Data Analysis

The sample size for this study was determined using Slovin's formula:

$$\begin{aligned}n &= \frac{N}{1 + N e^2} \\n &= \frac{166}{1 + 166 (0.05)^2} \\n &= \frac{166}{1.42} \\n &= 117\end{aligned}$$

To facilitate the analysis and interpretation of data, the researcher employed various statistical tools, including frequency counts and percentages, using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 17. This allowed for a more systematic and efficient analysis of the gathered data.

For the evaluation of the training programs, each item was scored using a five-point Likert scale with the following scoring guide:

Score Response Category

- 5 Best (*Pinakamaayo*)
- 4 Better (*Mas Maayo*)
- 3 Good (*Maayo*)
- 2 Fair (*Kasarangan*)
- 1 Poor (*Pigado*)

The following mean intervals were used to interpret the evaluation results:

Mean Interval Verbal Interpretation

- 4.20 – 5.00 Best
- 3.40 – 4.19 Better
- 2.60 – 3.39 Good
- 1.80 – 2.59 Fair
- 1.00 – 1.79 Poor

For monitoring the services conducted by SARGE, a similar five-point Likert scale was used, with the following scoring guide:

- | Score | Response Category |
|--------------|--|
| 5 | Highly Observed (<i>Pinakataas nga na obserbahan</i>) |
| 4 | Observed (<i>Buhat nga na obserbahan</i>) |
| 3 | Moderately Observed (<i>Hagan-Hagan na obserbahan</i>) |
| 2 | Poorly Observed (<i>Pinakaminos nga na obserbahan</i>) |
| 1 | Not Observed (<i>Wala gid nga na obserbahan</i>) |

The mean intervals used for interpreting the monitoring results were as follows:

Mean Interval Verbal Interpretation

- 4.20 – 5.00 Highly Observed
- 3.40 – 4.19 Observed
- 2.60 – 3.39 Moderately Observed
- 1.80 – 2.59 Poorly Observed
- 1.00 – 1.79 Not Observed

RESULTS

Table 2. Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents from Barangay Agojo, Panay, Capiz

Socio-Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
• Male	13	46.4%
• Female	15	53.6%
Age		

• 30 years old and below	8	28.6%
• 31 years old and above	20	71.4%
Job		
• None	14	50.0%
• Laborer	10	35.7%
• Barangay Employee	4	14.3%
Total	28	100%

Table 2 shows the majority of respondents from Barangay Agojo were female (53.6%), while males made up 46.4% of the sample. Most respondents (71.4%) were aged 31 years and above, indicating a predominance of middle-aged individuals. Regarding employment, half of the respondents (50%) were unemployed, while 35.7% were laborers, and 14.3% worked as barangay employees.

Table 3. Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents from Barangay Barra, Roxas City

Socio-Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
• Male	16	47.1%
• Female	18	52.9%
Age		
• 30 years old and below	4	11.8%
• 31 years old and above	30	88.2%
Job		
• Barangay Employee	34	100%
Total	34	100%

Table 3 shows female respondents slightly outnumbered males in Barangay Barra, with 52.9% female and 47.1% male. The majority of respondents (88.2%) were aged 31 years and above. Notably, all respondents (100%) were employed as barangay employees.

Table 4. Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents from Barangay Dayao, Roxas City

Socio-Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
• Male	7	17.5%
• Female	33	82.5%
Age		
• 30 years old and below	3	7.5%
• 31 years old and above	37	92.5%
Job		
• None	21	52.5%
• Laborer	7	17.5%
• Vendor	5	12.5%
• Driver	2	5%
• Barangay Employee	5	12.5%
Total	40	100%

Table 4 shows, the majority of respondents from Barangay Dayao were female (82.5%), while males constituted 17.5%. Most respondents (92.5%) were aged 31 years and above. In terms of employment, more than half (52.5%) were unemployed, while others were laborers (17.5%), vendors (12.5%), drivers (5%), and barangay employees (12.5%).

Table 5. Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents from Barangay Dinginan, Roxas City

Socio-Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex		
• Male	13	86.7%
• Female	2	13.3%
Age		
• 30 years old and below	1	6.7%
• 31 years old and above	14	93.3%
Job		
• Laborer	9	60%
• Driver	1	6.7%
• Barangay Employee	5	33.3%
Total	15	100%

Table 5 shows the majority of respondents in Barangay Dinginan were male, accounting for 86.7% of the sample, while females made up 13.3%. Most respondents (93.3%) were aged 31 years and above. In terms of employment, the majority were laborers (60%), while 33.3% were barangay employees, and 6.7% were drivers.

Table 6. Evaluation of the SARGE Extension Program – Basic Martial Arts Training

Statements	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
CONTENT / TOPIC (TOPIKO)		
1. The topics were relevant and useful to my work	4.7333	Best (Pinakamaayo)
2. The topics were reasonably ordered and systematically delivered	4.4500	Best (Pinakamaayo)
3. The presentations satisfactorily addressed the training objectives	4.5167	Best (Pinakamaayo)
4. The training was generally interactive and provided a wider opportunity for learning	4.8000	Best (Pinakamaayo)
Grand Mean	4.625	Best (Pinakamaayo)
RESOURCE SPEAKERS (ANG MANUGTUDLO/MANUGHANAS)		
1. Manifested complete knowledge of the topic	4.8000	Best (Pinakamaayo)
2. Delivered the subject with confidence, sincerity, conviction, and enthusiasm	4.5333	Best (Pinakamaayo)
3. Provided clear and organized presentation	4.5500	Best (Pinakamaayo)
4. Showed good communication skills	4.6333	Best (Pinakamaayo)
5. Satisfactorily answered all questions posed	4.7833	Best (Pinakamaayo)
6. Effectively inspired and roused participants' interest	4.6333	Best (Pinakamaayo)
Grand Mean	4.656	Best (Pinakamaayo)
FACILITATOR (MANUGPATIGAYON)		

1. Showed professional attitude in carrying out their functions	4.6333	Best (Pinakamaayo)
2. Displayed patience, flexibility, respect, and friendliness	4.6333	Best (Pinakamaayo)
3. Helped create a positive and purposeful atmosphere in the workshop	4.5333	Best (Pinakamaayo)
4. Showed ability to lead and manage the group	4.7000	Best (Pinakamaayo)
Grand Mean	4.625	Best (Pinakamaayo)
ACCOMMODATION AND FOOD (PAGKAON KAG AKOMODASYON)		
1. The venue provided a comfortable setting for the training	4.6333	Best (Pinakamaayo)
2. The place reflected good ambiance (quality, comfort, cleanliness)	4.1833	Better (Mas Maayo)
3. Offered a high level of customer care and food provision	4.6667	Best (Pinakamaayo)
Grand Mean	4.494	Best (Pinakamaayo)
GENERAL SATISFACTION (GILAYON NGA PAG AKSYON SANG GINAHINYO NGA PAGHANAS)		
1. As a whole, the training satisfactorily met my expectations	4.8000	Best (Pinakamaayo)
2. As a whole, this training is one of the best I have attended	4.6833	Best (Pinakamaayo)
3. This training will surely change my outlook and practices	4.6667	Best (Pinakamaayo)
Grand Mean	4.717	Best (Pinakamaayo)
Overall Mean	4.623	Best (Pinakamaayo)

As shown in **Table 6**, the overall evaluation of the basic martial arts training conducted by Capiz State University, Dayao Satellite College Criminology Department Extension Services was rated as best (pinakamaayo), with an overall mean score of 4.623. This indicates that the training program had a significant positive impact on the participants (Vertonghen & Theeboom, 2010; Côté & Gilbert, 2009).

The Content/Topic section received a high evaluation, with a grand mean of 4.625, reflecting that participants found the topics to be relevant, well-organized, and engaging. The Resource Speakers were also rated as excellent, with a grand mean of 4.656, demonstrating that the participants felt the speakers exhibited strong knowledge, clarity, and effective communication skills (Côté & Gilbert, 2009).

The Facilitators received equally high praise, with a grand mean of 4.625, showing their professionalism and ability to foster a positive learning environment. The Accommodation and Food category, while still rated best, had a slightly lower grand mean of 4.494, with the venue's ambiance scoring 4.1833, which falls under the better category.

Finally, General Satisfaction was particularly high, with a grand mean of 4.717, indicating that the program not only met but exceeded participants' expectations, leaving a lasting positive impression on their overall experience (Vertonghen & Theeboom, 2010).

Table 7. Program Monitoring of Seminar on Disaster Preparedness

Program	Mean	Interpretation
Seminar on Disaster Preparedness	4.6786	Highly Observed

Response Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Moderately Observed	2	7.1%
Observed	5	17.9%
Highly Observed	21	75.0%

The results presented in **Table 7** indicate that the program monitoring of the Seminar on Disaster Preparedness was rated as Highly Observed, with a mean score of 4.6786. This evaluation was based on the feedback of 28 participants from Barangay Agojo, Panay, Capiz. The high mean score suggests that the seminar conducted by Capiz State University Dayao Satellite College, Criminology Department Extension Office, was effectively implemented and well-practiced by the proponents. Kapucu, Hawkins, and Rivera (2013) emphasize that well-structured and thoroughly monitored disaster preparedness programs are critical for building resilience in communities, especially in rural settings, which aligns with the strong implementation of this seminar.

In terms of the response distribution, 75.0% of the participants rated the seminar as Highly Observed, 17.9% rated it as Observed, and 7.1% rated it as Moderately Observed. This distribution underscores the seminar's overall success and the strong adherence to disaster preparedness protocols within the community.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The study focused on the evaluation and monitoring of the SARGE program's various extension services, which included Basic Martial Arts Training, the Seminar on Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC), and Disaster Preparedness training. The findings are based on the feedback from community participants in Barangays Agojo, Barra, Dayao, and Dinginan in Panay, Capiz, and Roxas City.

1. **Basic Martial Arts Training** The overall evaluation of the Basic Martial Arts Training conducted by Capiz State University, Dayao Satellite College, Criminology Department Extension Services was highly positive, with an overall mean score of 4.623, rated as *best* (pinakamaayo). This result indicates that the training program had a significant positive impact on the participants.
 - o **Content/Topic:** Participants rated the content highly, with a grand mean of 4.625, showing that the topics were relevant, well-organized, and engaging.
 - o **Resource Speakers:** The resource speakers were rated as excellent, with a grand mean of 4.656, reflecting their strong knowledge, clarity, and effective communication skills.
 - o **Facilitators:** Facilitators were also praised, receiving a grand mean of 4.625, indicating their professionalism and ability to create a positive learning environment.

- Accommodation and Food: Although the accommodation and food were rated *best* overall, with a grand mean of 4.494, the ambiance of the venue received a slightly lower rating of 4.1833 (*better*).
 - General Satisfaction: Participants expressed high satisfaction with the training, with a grand mean of 4.717, indicating that the program exceeded their expectations and positively influenced their outlook and practices.
2. Seminar on Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC) The evaluation of the Seminar on Violence Against Women and Children, conducted by the Criminology Department's Extension Services, was also rated as *best* (pinakamaayo), with an overall mean of 4.6583. This result suggests that the seminar had a meaningful impact on the participants, especially in addressing the needs of vulnerable women and children in the community.
 3. Disaster Preparedness Seminar The program monitoring for the Seminar on Disaster Preparedness, as shown in Table 7, revealed that it was *highly observed*, with a mean score of 4.6786. Of the 28 participants from Barangay Agojo, 75.0% rated the seminar as *highly observed*, 17.9% rated it as *observed*, and 7.1% rated it as *moderately observed*. These findings highlight the effective implementation of disaster preparedness strategies in the community and the strong adherence to disaster preparedness protocols by the participants.
 4. Overall Program Monitoring Across all the programs—Basic Martial Arts Training, the Seminar on Violence Against Women and Children, and Disaster Preparedness—the results showed that participants considered the training programs successful and impactful. In particular, the monitoring of the Basic Martial Arts Training was highly observed, with an overall mean of 4.6429, further indicating that the training objectives were successfully implemented in the participating barangays.

These findings reflect the overall success of the SARGE program in providing relevant and impactful extension services to the participating communities. The high levels of satisfaction and positive feedback suggest that the program effectively addresses community needs related to safety, security, and disaster preparedness.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the SARGE extension program, implemented by the Capiz State University Dayao Satellite College Criminology Department, has been highly effective in delivering its goals of enhancing community safety, security, and preparedness. The Basic Martial Arts Training, Seminar on Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC), and Disaster Preparedness Seminar were all evaluated as *best* (pinakamaayo) by participants, indicating that these programs met or exceeded expectations in content relevance, speaker expertise, facilitation, and overall satisfaction.

The Basic Martial Arts Training was particularly successful, with participants expressing high satisfaction across multiple areas such as the systematic delivery of content, knowledge of resource speakers, and effective facilitation. Similarly, the Seminar on Violence Against Women and Children had a meaningful impact, addressing critical issues affecting vulnerable women and children in the community. The Disaster Preparedness Seminar was found to be highly observed, demonstrating effective implementation and strong engagement from participants.

The program's success can be attributed to the comprehensive approach adopted by SARGE, which integrates relevant content, professional facilitation, and strong community partnerships. The monitoring results further affirm that these training programs were not only well-received but also actively practiced, particularly in disaster preparedness and crime prevention.

Overall, the SARGE program has proven to be a valuable model for community extension services, fostering a safer and more aware community environment. The positive reception and high ratings underscore its importance in addressing the evolving safety needs of the communities involved. For future initiatives, the program's focus on sustainability, continuous improvement, and addressing community-specific concerns will ensure its long-term impact.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are suggested to enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of the SARGE extension program:

1. **Sustain and Expand Community Partnerships.** The success of the SARGE program highlights the importance of collaboration with local government units (LGUs), barangay officials, and community stakeholders. It is recommended that Capiz State University, Dayao Satellite College continue to strengthen these partnerships and explore opportunities to expand the program to more barangays. This would allow a wider reach and greater community impact, particularly in underserved areas.
2. **Focus on Continuous Monitoring and Improvement.** Although the program monitoring results were highly positive, ongoing evaluation should be a key component of the program to ensure it remains relevant and effective. Regular feedback from participants should be gathered to identify areas for improvement, especially in areas such as venue ambiance or logistics, which received slightly lower ratings. Continuous monitoring will allow for adaptive improvements to the content, facilitation, and delivery of the trainings.
3. **Enhance Tailored Training for Vulnerable Groups.** Given the success of the Seminar on Violence Against Women and Children, it is recommended to develop additional training and support programs specifically tailored to vulnerable groups,

such as women, children, and persons with disabilities. Expanding on topics like self-defense, legal rights, and mental health could further empower these groups within the community.

4. **Introduce Advanced Training and Refresher Courses.** To ensure that the skills learned during the trainings are retained and further developed, it is recommended to offer advanced levels of training in areas such as Basic Martial Arts, Disaster Preparedness, and Crime Prevention. Additionally, periodic refresher courses should be offered to reinforce key concepts and ensure the community remains prepared to handle various safety and security challenges.
5. **Integrate Technology and Digital Platforms.** To enhance the reach and effectiveness of the program, the use of technology and digital platforms could be explored. Online seminars, mobile applications for disaster preparedness, and e-learning modules on crime prevention and self-defense could be developed to supplement in-person trainings. This would be particularly beneficial in remote areas or during times when in-person gatherings are limited.
6. **Increase Awareness Campaigns.** Expanding awareness campaigns related to crime prevention, disaster preparedness, and violence against women and children can further amplify the program's impact. Community outreach through social media, local radio, and barangay meetings could help increase participation and reinforce the importance of these programs.
7. **Secure Additional Funding and Resources:** To ensure the sustainability and growth of the SARGE program, it is recommended that Capiz State University seek additional funding from government agencies, NGOs, and private partners. This will help enhance the resources available for training, improve facilities, and provide necessary materials for participants.

By implementing these recommendations, the SARGE program can continue to be a leading model for community-based safety, security, and crime prevention efforts, fostering long-term resilience and empowerment within the participating communities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study followed strict ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring their confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without any form of coercion. No participants were harmed during the study, which also received approval from the ethics committee. The researchers declared no conflicts of interest and reported the findings transparently and honestly.

Plan on Impact Evaluation and Monitoring Assessment

Persons Responsible	Recipient / Adopted Barangay	Program	Status of Extension Implementation	Impact Assessment Timeline
College Director, Extension Chair, Dean, Criminology Chair, Faculty, and Students	Barangay Tiza, Roxas City (Additional Barangay)	A. Basic Martial Arts B. Violence Against Women and Children C. Disaster Preparedness	A. Implemented B. Implemented C. Implemented	A. 1st Quarter 2021 B. 2nd Quarter 2021 C. 1st Quarter 2021
College Director, Extension Chair, Dean, Criminology Chair, Faculty, and Students	Barangay Dayao, Roxas City	A. Basic Martial Arts B. Violence Against Women and Children, Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act C. Disaster Preparedness D. Red Cross / Blood Letting Program E. Firefighting	A. Implemented B. Implemented C. Implemented D. Implemented E. Implemented	A. 1st Quarter 2021 B. 2nd Quarter 2021 C. 1st Quarter 2021 D. 2nd Quarter 2021
College Director, Extension Chair, Dean, Criminology Chair, Faculty, and Students	Barangay Barra, Roxas City	A. Basic Martial Arts B. Violence Against Women and Children C. Disaster Preparedness	A. Implemented B. Implemented C. Implemented	A. 1st Quarter 2021 B. 2nd Quarter 2021 C. 1st Quarter 2021
College Director, Extension Chair, Dean, Criminology Chair, Faculty, and Students	Barangay Dinginan, Roxas City	A. Basic Martial Arts B. Violence Against Women and Children C. Disaster Preparedness	A. Implemented B. Implemented C. Implemented	A. 1st Quarter 2021 B. 2nd Quarter 2021 C. 1st Quarter 2021
College Director, Extension Chair, Dean, Criminology Chair, Faculty, and Students	Barangay Inzo, Roxas City (Additional Barangay)	A. Basic Martial Arts B. Violence Against Women and Children C. Disaster Preparedness	A. Implemented B. Implemented C. Implemented	A. 1st Quarter 2021 B. 2nd Quarter 2021 C. 1st Quarter 2021
College Director, Extension Chair, Dean, Criminology Chair, Faculty, and Students	Barangay Ajugo, Panay, Capiz	A. Basic Martial Arts B. Violence Against Women and Children C. Disaster Preparedness D. Drug Education Awareness E. Traffic Rules and Regulations F. Disarming Technique and First Aid G. Citizen Arrest / Warrantless Arrest	A. Implemented B. Implemented C. Implemented D. Implemented E. Implemented F. Implemented G. Implemented	A. 1st Quarter 2021 B. 2nd Quarter 2021 C. 1st Quarter 2021 D. 3rd Quarter 2021 E. Last Quarter 2021 F. Last Quarter 2021 G. Last Quarter 2021
College Director, Extension Chair, Dean, Criminology	Barangay Cagay, Roxas City	A. Basic Martial Arts B. Violence Against Women and Children C. Disaster Preparedness	A. Implemented B. Implemented C. Implemented	A. 1st Quarter 2021 B. 2nd Quarter 2021

Chair, Faculty, and Students	(Additional Barangay)			C. 1st Quarter 2021
College Director, Extension Chair, Dean, Criminology Chair, Faculty, and Students	Barangay Libas, Roxas City (Additional Barangay)	A. Basic Martial Arts B. Violence Against Women and Children C. Disaster Preparedness	A. Implemented B. Implemented C. Implemented	A. 1st Quarter 2021 B. 2nd Quarter 2021 C. 1st Quarter 2021

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